

Gamma Function – New Approximation

i.e. Buczak's Gamma Method

Jakub Buczak

Factorials play a fundamental role in mathematics, particularly when expressed as fractions. While traditional methods often rely on integration to derive solutions, my approach is designed to be calculator-friendly, utilizing straightforward operations. Although several non-calculus-based approximations exist, my method stands out due to its unique structure, consisting of only a few distinct terms. This approximation can be easily computed on standard calculators, including those available on mobile devices, and achieves a rather impressive accuracy with an error margin of approximately 0.02% to 0.05%, however 0.1% appears to be the upper limit for most extreme cases.

The formula takes the following shape:

$$n! \approx \left[\frac{a}{b} (\lceil n \rceil!)^{\frac{1}{\lceil n \rceil}} + \frac{c}{b} (\lfloor n \rfloor!)^{\frac{1}{\lfloor n \rfloor}} \right]^n = \left[\frac{a}{b} \sqrt[\lceil n \rceil]{\lceil n \rceil!} + \frac{c}{b} \sqrt[\lfloor n \rfloor]{\lfloor n \rfloor!} \right]^n$$

where $\frac{a}{b} + \frac{c}{b} = 1$

In this context, the symbol $n!$ denotes the final result of a fractional factorial, where n represents the numerical value associated with the factorial. The variables a, b and c act as weight factors that enhance the approximation of the exact value by allowing for greater emphasis on either the ceiling or floor of n , which are also incorporated within the formula.

To understand the derivation of the formula, we will first assume that our factorials operate within this numerical system:

$$X_n^n = n! = n(n-1)(n-2)\dots(n-n+1)$$

We can now determine X by applying fundamental properties of logarithms.

$$[\log(X_n^n) = \log(n!)] \implies [n \log(X_n) = \log(n!)]$$

$$\left[X_n = 10^{\frac{\log(n!)}{n}} \right] \implies \left[X_n = (n!)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right]$$

If n is a whole number (such as 1, 2, 3, etc.), it is straightforward to determine X using the formula we derived. However, we still need to establish a method for calculating X when n is a fractional value. This is where the ceiling and weighted factors a, b and c become relevant. The formula operates by first identifying the ceiling and floor of the given number, followed by the application of the weighted factors a, b and c .

These weight factors are essential for approximation. To illustrate their significance, let us consider the fractional value $n=4.25$ as an example. In this case, the weight factors are skewed more towards 4 rather than 5, as 4 is numerically closer to 4.25. Consequently, the weight factors would be 0.75 for 4 and 0.25 for 5. This approach effectively distributes these values on a scale, ensuring that they align appropriately.

For example, when $n = 4.25$, the formula would take the following shape:

$$4.25! \approx \left[\frac{1}{4}(5!)^{\frac{1}{5}} + \frac{3}{4}(4!)^{\frac{1}{4}} \right]^{4.25}$$

Based on the logic we have outlined, we can represent our results graphically as a function.

$$f(x) = \left(\sqrt[x]{x!} \right)^x$$

The function represented on the graph closely resembles the basic function $f(x)=x!$. However, it is important to note that there are no negative values present on the graph.

Using a function as a representation, we can get a better understanding on why the formula produces such little error with this equation:

$$f(x) = \sqrt[x]{x!}$$

As observed, the graph closely resembles a straight line, indicating that approximating the value using weight factors is a viable solution. This close alignment is a key reason the formula yields a minimal error. However, it is important to note that while the graph approaches a straight line, it is not perfectly linear, which is the reason for the minimal error.